

Undergraduates' Computer Literacy and Parents' Education Level as Correlates of their Use of E-resources in University Libraries in North-West, Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: Use of technology and socioeconomic factors are two known correlates. The main purpose of this study was to determine the correlation amongst undergraduates' computer literacy, parents' educational level and their use of e-resources in university libraries in North-West, Nigeria.

Method: A correlational research design was used for the study. The population of the study was 10,239 300 level registered students in seven federal university libraries in the 2023/2024 academic session. Multistage sampling procedure was adopted. The sample size of the study was 370 determined using the Krejcie and Morgan table. Instrument for data collection was an achievement test and a questionnaire developed by the researcher from the UNESCO's "Global Framework of Reference on Digital Literacy Skills" and opinions and findings from reviewed literature. The instrument was validated by three experienced lecturers. Kuder-Richardson 20 and Cronbach Alpha methods were used to determine internal consistencies for the achievement test-CLAT) and the questionnaire-UUE-RQ respectively. They yielded 0.96 and 0.82 co-efficient values respectively. Direct approach method was used by the researcher aided by six assistants to collect data for

the study and a return rate of 92% was recorded. Data were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation (r) was used for the analysis using SPSS v.21.

Findings/Results: The findings indicate among other things that there is a positive and weak correlation among computer literacy, parents' educational level and undergraduates' use of e-resources in university libraries in North-West, Nigeria. It also reveals a statistical significant relationship amongst them.

Implications: The implication of the study is that there is a probable gap in use, as students from higher parents' educational level may have greater access to technology and educational resources as against those from lower parents' educational level who may face barriers, such as limited access to the internet or computers, which could either enhance or hinder their development of digital literacy to engage with e-resources.

Conclusion: The study concludes that there is a correlation among digital literacy, parents' education level and undergraduates use of e-resources in university libraries in North-West, Nigeria.

Recommendations: It was recommended among other things that universities in North-West, Nigeria should strengthen their computer literacy programme and introduce financial aid to take care of students' from low social economic background to help bridge the access and use gap.

Keywords: Undergraduates, Computer Literacy, Parents' Education, Use of E-resources, University Libraries, North-West, Nigeria

Introduction

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has significantly influenced the evolution and advancements of libraries, aligning with the Fifth Law of Library Science by Ranganathan, which states that "Library is a growing organism". This evolution and advancement led to the integration of ICT resources such as the electronic information resources, (e-resources) into library services and operations. They includes e-journals, e-books, e-databases, Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC), online archives/repositories have revolutionised traditional library services by enhancing accessibility and efficiency thereby fulfilling the Fourth Law of Library Science, "Save the

time of the reader” through provision of up-to-date information, convenience and rapid retrieval capabilities

Therefore, effective utilisation of e-resources depends on students' computer literacy, which involves operating technological devices and software applications for accessing and managing digital content. UNESCO (2018), in its Digital Literacy Global Framework, identifies six competency areas, with device and software operations (computer literacy) as number one. This implies that it is the basic of the required skills, because e-resources are held and accessible through hardware devices and its operating software (Salman, Ahmed, Raheem & Pelemo, 2020). Requisite computer literacy skills, such as, booting and shutting down the computer, troubleshooting for technical issues, accessing and retrieving information from the Web pages (WWW), file management, navigating e-learning platforms, operating personal computers independently, and utilising software applications for document preparation, among others are expected from the undergraduates if they must make effective use of the available e-resources.

Computer literacy is the ability to manipulate both the hardware and software components of a computer or digital device to effectively access and communicate information. Hence, inadequate computer skills significantly impede students' utilisation of online information resources (Odede, 2015). North-West region may not be an exception. North-West, Nigeria is a geographical zone characterized by high poverty rate, thereby giving it a low socioeconomic status. Majority of the people are subsistent farmers and herders. Giving the high cost of technology and its rapid innovations, the family backgrounds' capabilities of acceptance and ownership of digital devices that would help give their children early exposure with computers are in doubt. Rightly to this, e-library use statistics in the universities in the North-West region shows low utilization of the resources by the students, again, the researcher's observations shows that many of the undergraduates find it difficult to make use of the provided computers independently. They are seen sitting in front of the computers fiddling with it, unable to boot the computer, some could not open applications, perform file management among other shortcomings. These makes their effective use of e-resources difficult, some of them with these challenges shy away from coming to the e-library. According to Igbo (2020), these are evidence of lack of computer literacy. This is worrisome considering the huge investments, benefits and efforts put in place to ensure availability, access, and usage of these e-resources.

Factors contributing to this include low adoption rates of ICT (Gulbahar, 2007 in Attuquayefio, Achampong, and Aryeetey, 2014) and socioeconomic barriers that limit access to technology (Krish et al., 2018; Mubarak et al., 2020). The digital divide remains a pressing concern, especially in developing countries like Nigeria, particularly, the North-West where differences in technology access can significantly affect use of e-resources for an enhanced educational outcome. Attending to these issues is essential for promoting computer literacy and ensuring students' engagement with online resources. In addition to computer literacy, the education level of parents (their education attainment/qualification in relation to others), which is a socioeconomic factor plays a vital role in students' ability to use e-resources and according to Bakar (2014) it influences their academic performance. Quadri (2013) agrees that parents' educational attainment significantly impacts their children's academic achievements, including usage of e-resources for assignments and research projects. This implies that higher-educated parents will encourage and supports their children's use of digital technologies. Obviously, in North-West Nigeria, low socioeconomic status and its educational challenges may impede children's early exposure and use of digital technology.

Various studies have been conducted on the computer literacy of undergraduates, examining their skills and competencies, including their levels of skills and relationships in various parts of the world, including Nigeria, but none have investigated the relationship between computer literacy and parents' educational levels and undergraduates' use of e-resources in North-West Nigeria and the correlation among them. This study aims to determine the correlation among computer literacy, parents' educational level and undergraduates' use of e-resources in university libraries in North-West, Nigeria. It will therefore fill a critical gap in literature by determining the interaction between computer literacy and parental education levels in higher education, thereby providing insight on the use of e-resources in the region.

Statement of the Problem

The increasing reliance on e-resources by university libraries across the world, including North-West, Nigeria, where huge investments and efforts are made to ensure their availability, accessibility is noticeable. However, the utilization rate is not commensurable with the efforts, thus, the preliminary investigation by the researcher shows that a lot of undergraduates in universities in North-West, Nigeria have not been able to show good computer literacy skills, perhaps as a result of their family background. This means that without the assistance of fellow students or e-library staff they would not be able to use

the computers thereby hindering their effective use of available e-resources and limit their academic success. There is therefore need to know the relationship between computer literacy, parents' educational level and the use of e-resources in North-West, Nigeria. Hence, this study was set to determine undergraduates' computer literacy, parents' education level as correlates of use of e-resources in university libraries in North-West, Nigeria and fill the critical gap in understanding the interplay amongst these variables.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of the study is to determine undergraduates' computer literacy and parents' educational level as correlates of undergraduates' use of electronic information resources in university libraries in North-West, Nigeria.

Specifically, the study seeks to determine:

1. the type of relationship that exists among undergraduates' computer literacy skills and their use of e-resources in university libraries in North-West, Nigeria;
2. the type of relationship that exists between parents' education level and undergraduates' use of e-resources in university libraries in North-West, Nigeria; and
3. the correlation amongst undergraduates computer literacy, parents' education level and their use of e-resources.

Hypotheses

- Ho₁:** There is a significant relationship between undergraduates' computer literacy and their use of e-resources in university libraries in North-West, Nigeria.
- Ho₂:** There is a significant relationship between undergraduates' parents' educational level and their use of e-resources in university libraries in North-West, Nigeria.
- Ho₃:** There is a significant correlation among undergraduates' computer literacy, parents' educational level and use of e-resources in university libraries in, North-West, Nigeria

Theoretical Framework

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

The basic tents of the theory is that computer systems cannot improve organizational performance unless they are accepted and used. The model was propounded in 1989 by

Davis et al. TAM suggests that acceptance is expressed in individual behavior and attitudes.

TAM has two main elements. These elements are Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) and Perceived Usefulness (PU). According to Davies et. al., they are central elements in determining computer acceptance behaviours. These elements help in explaining how human attitude and behaviour amidst other external variables can lead to the use of technology or otherwise. PEOU explains that if the user believes that he can use the technology with minimal efforts he will accept to use the technology while PU holds that when a potential user believes that the technology will be useful to him in his assignment, he is most likely going to use it and vice-versa when he feels otherwise. On the other hand, the two elements influence a user's Attitude Towards Use (ATU) which also affects the person's Behaviourial Intention to Use (BIU) and leads to Actual Use (AU) of the technology.

TAM, even though a popular model for understanding acceptance and use of technology used over the years has a bias. TAM was originally meant for acceptance and use of computer systems for organization workers where the use of technology is compulsory. The workers of the organization are expected to use the technology in their daily routines to enhance organization performance. This limits the potentials of TAM, however, it has been successfully applied to voluntary areas such as students using it for learning. The use of e-resources by undergraduate is voluntary, though a necessity. TAM's consideration of only two elements (PU and PEOU) is considered a limitation of other possible factors that could influence adoption and use of technology. TAM, however, through its external variable window allows for extension of the model. This paper introduces socio-educational factors such of parents' education and skill-based factors such as computer literacy to extend TAM. E-resources is a digital learning resources provided by university libraries to enhance students' academic performance. It therefore requires that students' make effective use of it to achieve desired performance.

TAM can therefore be applied to this paper in the sense that, Computer Literacy (CL) affects PEOU as students with good computer skills will find e-resources easier to use and may also recognise its benefits (PU) due to their familiarity with digital tools. On the other hand, Parents' Educational Level indirectly affects PU and PEOU. This is because, parents with higher education understands the usefulness of digital resources in this era and would most likely encourage their children to acquire digital literacy which will in turn boost their confidence that they can use the resources with minimal efforts. These imply

that computer literacy skill and parents' education level affects PU and PEOU which in turn influence attitude toward use (ATU) which affects behavioural intention to Use (BIU) and ultimately leads to actual use (AU) of e-resources. Positive perceptions lead to better attitudes and behavioral intentions, such as acquiring digital literacy skills and developing computer self-efficacy. This study suggests that understanding and applying the theory's basic tenets can significantly improve undergraduates' attitudes towards developing computer literacy, leading to effective use of e-resources. Hence, suggesting a relationship amongst the variables.

Fig. 1: TAM Model by Davies et. al. (1989) modified by the researcher.

Review of Related Literature

Relationship between Computer Literacy Skills and Undergraduates' Use of E-resources

The integration of e-resources into library collections has significantly impacted academic research and information retrieval. These resources offer benefits like quick access, space conservation, multi-user capabilities, and portability. However, effective use requires computer literacy skills among undergraduates. Mabawonku, Adekunmisi, Oyedipe, and Olusanya (2023) explores the impact of computer literacy skills on

electronic resource usage among undergraduates at Babcock University, South-West, Nigeria. The findings highlighted skills such as accessing information from the World Wide Web (WWW), navigating e-learning platforms, operating personal computers independently, and utilizing software applications for document preparation as necessary skills posed by their respondents that enables them use e-resources..

Aboyade et al. (2021) explored the relationship between computer competency levels and the use of digital databases among engineering technology students in Nigerian polytechnics and reveals that students with moderate computer competency exhibited a high and significant use of word processing, digital databases and practical problem-solving skills, thereby being able to retrieve relevant information which positively impacted their academic performance. Similar study by Sambo and Precious (2022) examined the relationship between students' computer hardware and software skills in the use of electronic information resources in university libraries in South-West Nigeria. Their findings reveal a moderate positive and significant relationship between students' computer skills and their use of e-resources. The study indicates a high and significant correlation for the joint relationship between hardware and software skills, highlighting the need for comprehensive computer literacy programmes that involve both aspects. This holistic approach could significantly enhance students' ability to manipulate and utilize e-resources effectively. Additionally, Amuda, Kehinde, Abdul, and Onanuga (2020) investigated the predictors of undergraduates' use of e-resources at Al-Hikmah University, Kwara State, North-Central, Nigeria. Their study concluded that there is a significant relationship between computer literacy and the utilization of electronic resources. These emphasise the indication that computer literacy is a critical factor of students' utilization of digital materials.

Relationship between Undergraduates' Computer Literacy, Parents' Education Level, and their Use of E-resources

The relationship between parents' education level (socioeconomic status) and students' academic performance is a critical area of study in understanding the factors that influence undergraduates' utilization of e-resources. The educational attainment of parents significantly impacts their children's academic outcomes, particularly in the context of using electronic resources for academic activities.

Research suggests that parents with higher educational levels are more likely to engage in their children's education (Grissmer, 2003). Such parents often provide access to digital

technologies and encourage participation in digital training, thereby enhancing their children confidence and interest in exploring library e-resources. This early exposure to technology is crucial, as it can determine students' willingness to utilize available digital materials for their academic needs.

The literature consistently highlights the positive correlation between parental education and students' academic achievements, including their engagement with information and communication technology (ICT). Yang, Barnard-Brak, and Siwatu (2018) found that approximately 35% of the relationship between socioeconomic status and academic achievement could be attributed to the availability of ICT resources. This finding underscores the importance of access to technology, which is often facilitated by parents' educational backgrounds. Ozo (2007) also established a significant difference in academic performance among students based on their parents' education levels, asserting that parental educational attainment is a critical factor that influences students' success, including their use of ICT. In addition, research by Peng and Yu (2022) indicates that parents' education levels are pivotal in shaping students' digital literacy. This relationship is further corroborated by Diogo, Silva, and Viana (2018) and Tran, Ho, and Phametal (2022), who found a positive correlation between parental education and students' digital literacy skills. Similarly, Foo, Majid, and Azura Mokhtaretal (2014) highlighted that the educational attainment of fathers significantly influences the digital literacy of secondary students.

Methodology

The study adopted correlational research design Population of the study consists of 10, 239 300 level students from seven Federal universities in North-West, Nigeria registered in the 024/2025 academic session. The study used 300 level students in line with Amkpa and Imam (2011) position that fresher activities do not allow 100 level students to use the library as they should and Hayelom (2014) that students' use of library resources increases as they progress in their studies. The sample size of the study was 370 undergraduates registered with the university library in the seven selected universities. Multi-stage sampling techniques was used in this study. There is a total of 42 universities (federal, state and private owned) in the zone. Purposeful sampling was used to select one federal university from each of the seven states in the zone giving a total of seven universities. Krejcie and Morgan formula table for determining sample size from a given population was used. Hayes, (2024) formula, $\text{Sample size} \div \text{Population size} \times \text{population of sub-group}$ was used to arrive at the number of instrument for each library (sub-group).

The instrument for data collection was an achievement test used for the computer literacy skills and a questionnaire for the parents' educational level and undergraduates' use of e-resources. The instruments were developed from the UNESCO (2018) Global Framework of Reference on Digital Literacy Skills for Indicator 4.4.2; Krish et al (2018) and opinions and findings from reviewed literature. The face and content validation of the instruments were done by three experienced lecturers from the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. They assessed the clarity, relevance, appropriateness and suitability of the instructions and contents of the instruments. The reliability of the instrument was established using the Kuder-Richardson 20 for the achievement test and Cronbach Alpha for the questionnaire. Twenty (20) copies of the instruments were administered randomly to 300 level undergraduate students of Abubakar Tafawa Belawa University Bauchi (ATBU), Bauchi State, North-East, Nigeria which is also a Federal University, which were not part of the study area but shared similar features with the North-West. The internal consistency of the items in each part of the instrument was then determined. Thus, Undergraduates' Computer Literacy Skills (UCLS) yielded coefficient value of 0.96 while Undergraduates' Use of E-resources in University Libraries (UUEUL) has a coefficient value of 0.82. A total of 370 copies of the instruments were administered to the respondents in their various libraries by the researcher with the help of seven research assistants through direct administration and retrieval method and collected as they finish. The data collected for the study were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Three Null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 significance level.

Results and discussion

Presentation of Results

Table 1: Population, Sample size and Instrument distribution and

S/N	Name of University	300 Level R.L.U.	S. S. /D. Q.	U. Q.	Return Rate (%)
1	Federal University Dutse, Jigawa State	417	15	15	
2	Bayero University Kano (BUK), Kano State	3,234	117	112	
3	Ahmadu Bello University (ABU), Zaria, Kaduna State	175	6	6	
4	Federal University Dutsin-ma, Katsina State	785	28	27	
5	Federal University Gusau, Zamfara State	883	32	29	
6	Usumanu Danfodyio University Sokoto, Sokoto State	4,041	146	127	
7	Federal University Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi State	706	26	24	
Total		10,239	370	340	92

Key: R.L.U=Registered Library Users; S.S=Sample Size; D.Q=Distributed Questionnaire; U.Q. =Used Questionnaire

Table 2: Parents Highest Education Level Frequency and Percentage Response of the Respondents

	Variable	Number	Frequency	%
Parent's Highest Education Level	Did not go to school	340	31	9.1
	First School Leaving Certificate (FSLC)		20	5.9
	GCE/WAEC/NABTEB/SSCE		110	32.4
	Diploma		38	11.2
	NCE		44	12.9
	First Degree/HND/PGD		51	15
	Masters		30	8.8
	Ph.D		16	4.8
	Total			340

The analysis presented in Table 2 reveals the frequency and percentage response of the sample population on their parent's highest educational level. Parent's, with

GCE/WAEC/NABTEB/SSCE and those with First Degree/HND/PGD had the highest percentage responses of 110 (32.4%) and 51 (15%) respectively. WHILE Master's Degree and PhD has the least responses of 30 (8.8%) and 16 (4.8%) respectively.

Research question 1 and Hypothesis 1

Research question 1: What is the relationship that exists between undergraduates' computer literacy and their use of e-resources in university libraries in North-West, Nigeria?

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics showing the undergraduates' computer literacy and their use of e-resources in university libraries in North-West, Nigeria

Item	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Undergraduate Use of E-Resources	70.5059	17.13705	340
Computer Literacy Skills	55.8676	22.42885	340

The result of table 3 is the descriptive analysis. It shows that the dependent variable, undergraduate use of e-resources has the highest mean score of 70.5059 computer literacy has a mean score of 55.8676.

The relationship and the hypothesis result

Hypothesis 1: There is a significant relationship between undergraduates' computer literacy and undergraduates' use of e-resources in university libraries in North-West, Nigeria.

Table 4: Pearson correlation on the undergraduates' computer literacy and their use of e-resources in university libraries in North-West, Nigeria

Sources of Variations	N	Df	Computer Literacy Skills	Undergraduates' Use of E-resources	Remark
Computer Literacy Skills	340	338	1	0.183 0.001	Positive Weak Relationship
Undergraduates' Use of E-resources	340	338	0.183 0.001	1	Significant

Table 4 shows an r value of 0.183 suggesting a positive weak relationship. It also indicates that at the common alpha level of 0.05 level and 338 df, a P-value of 0.001 is less than

the common alpha level leading to the rejection of the null hypotheses and the alternate hypothesis was accepted

Research question 2 and Hypothesis 2

Research question 2: Do a relationship exists between undergraduates' parent's education level and their use of e-resources in university libraries in North-West, Nigeria?

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics showing the parents' education level and undergraduates' use of e-resources in university libraries in North-West, Nigeria

Item	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Undergraduate Use of E-Resources	70.5059	17.13705	340
Parent's Education Level	4.1676	1.90748	340

Table 5 presents the result of the descriptive analysis which shows that the dependent variable, undergraduate use of e-resources has a high mean score of 70.5059 while parents' education has a mean score of 4.1676.

The relationship and the hypothesis result

Hypothesis 2: There is a significant relationship between undergraduates' parent's educational level and their use of e-resources in university libraries in North-West, Nigeria.

Table 6: Pearson correlation on the undergraduates' parent's education level and use of e-resources in university libraries in North-West, Nigeria

Sources of Variations	N	Df	Parent's Education Level	Undergraduates' Use of E-resources	Remark
Parent's Education Level	340	338	1	0.129 0.018	Positive Weak Relationship
Undergraduates' Use of E-resources	340	338	0.129 0.018	1	Significant

The result from table 6 presents an r of 0.129, indicating that a positive weak relationship exists between undergraduates' parent's education level and use of e-resources in

university libraries in North-West, Nigeria. The statistics result shows that at 0.05 significance level of significance a P-value of **0.018** is less than 0.05, the alternate hypothesis was accepted.

Research question 3 and Hypothesis 3

Research question 3: What is the correlation among undergraduates’ computer literacy, parents’ educational level and use of e-resources in university libraries in North-West, Nigeria?

Table 7: Descriptive Statistics showing the parents’ education level and undergraduates’ use of e-resources in university libraries in North-West, Nigeria

<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>N</i>
Undergraduate Use of E-Resources	70.5059	17.13705	340
Parent's Education Level	4.1676	1.90748	340
Computer Literacy	55.8676	22.42885	340

Table 7 is the result of the descriptive analysis of the variables. It shows that the dependent variable, undergraduates’ use of e-resources has the highest mean score of 70.5059 followed by computer literacy with a mean score of 55.8676.

Hypothesis 3: There is a significant joint correlation among undergraduates’ computer literacy, parents’ educational level and use of e-resources in university libraries in North-West, Nigeria.

Table 8: Summary of regression analysis on the correlation amongst undergraduates’ computer literacy, parents’ educational level and use of e-resources in university libraries in North-west, Nigeria

Models	R	R-Square	Adjusted R-Square	Df	Cal. F	P-Value	Remark
Computer Literacy, Parents Educational Level and Undergraduates’ use of e-resource	.241	.058	.053	388	10.399	.000	Positive Weak Correlation
							Significant

Table 8 above is the summary result of the correlation coefficient of multiple regression analysis between computer literacy, parents’ educational level and undergraduates’ use of e-resources. It shows that r is .241 with an R Square of .058 indicating a positive weak correlation amongst the variables. The hypothesis test indicates that at 0.05 level of

significance, a 3df numerator and 388df denominator, a calculated F of 10.399, the P-value .000 is less than 0.05, leading to the acceptance of the alternate hypothesis which states that there is a significant joint correlation among undergraduates' computer literacy, parents' education level and use of e-resources in university libraries in North-West, Nigeria.

Table 9: The Result of Multiple Regression Analysis on computer literacy, parents' education level and use of e-resources in university libraries in North-West, Nigeria.

		Use of E-resources	Parent Education Level	Computer Literacy
Pearson Correlation	Use of E-resources	1.000	-.129	.183
	Parent Education	-.129	1.000	.146
Sig. (1tailed)	Computer Literacy	.183	.146	1.000
	Use of E-resources Parent Education	.009	.009	.003
N	Computer Literacy	.000	.003	.
	Use of E-resources Parent Education	340	340	340
Level	Computer Literacy	340	340	340
	Computer Literacy	340	340	340

Table 9 is the result of the multiple regression analysis of the variables.

Discussion of the finding

The study aimed at determining the correlation/relationship among computer literacy, parents' education level and undergraduates' use of e-resources in university libraries in North-West, Nigeria. The finding for research question one reveals a positive weak relationship between computer literacy and the use of e-resources among undergraduates in North-West, Nigeria. This outcome is expected and significant given that computer literacy is a basic skill need which confers the student the ability to manipulate both the hard and software components of the device where the e-resources are held to be able to access the e-resources without which the student would be struggling to use e-resources.

This finding is in line with earlier reports which revealed that there is a relationship between computer literacy and use of e-resources (Sambo and Precious, 2022), though moderate and Mabawonku, et al. (2023) who found very high level positive relationships between students' computer literacy skills and their use of e-resources in university libraries. The difference in the two differing results may not be surprising considering the influence of socioeconomic status. While that of Mabawonku, et al., (2023) was conducted in a private university, Sambo and Precious (2022) was in public universities both in South-West, Nigeria with a relatively higher socioeconomic status which afforded them the luxury of technology compared to the North-West with low socioeconomic status.

However, this strength of relationship is not strong enough to infer a meaningful connection. This means that there is some association, but it is likely not significant in practical terms and cannot imply that higher computer literacy alone will lead to significantly higher usage of e-resources. On the other hand, the hypothesis test indicates a statistically significant relationship between undergraduates' computer literacy and their use of e-resources in university libraries in North-West, Nigeria. This is also expected because knowledge of digital technology is required to use digital resources like the e-resources. The finding is consistent with that of Amuda, et. al., (2020) which showed that there is a statistical significant relationship between undergraduates' computer literacy and their use of electronic resources at Al-Hikmah University, Kwara State, Nigeria.

Research question 2 result indicates a positive weak relationship between undergraduates' parent's education level and their use of e-resources in university libraries in North-West, Nigeria. This confirms the assumption that as parents achieve higher educational qualifications, there is likelihood that their children will make use of e-resources, though, marginally. Educated parents understands that we live in an era where everything including education is driven by digital technology, so they will ensure that their children build capacity for effective utilization of digital technology including e-resources which will be useful in their academic performances. However, in the context of North-West, Nigeria, with low socioeconomic status, access to technology by children, especially early in life which could help them develop computer self-efficacy and willingness to accept and use technology could be a contributing factor for the weak relationship, hence, understanding this relationship is crucial for developing strategies that will enhance e-resource accessibility for all

However, there is no literature on the relationship between parent's educational level and undergraduates' use of e-resources in university libraries, but, the findings from pre-

tertiary schools aligns with this study, for example, Diogo, et. al., (2018) and Tran, et. al., (2022) shows that students' digital literacy positively correlates with parents' education and Ozo (2007) also established a significant difference in academic performance among students based on their parents' education levels. The hypothesis test suggests that there is a statistically significant positive relationship between undergraduates' parent's educational level and their use of e-resources in university libraries in North-West, Nigeria. It indicates a reliable correlation.

The result of the joint correlation amongst computer literacy, parents' educational level and use of e-resources by undergraduates' in North-West, Nigeria indicates a positive weak correlation amongst them. Again, the finding shows that there is a relationship amongst the three variables. While the basic skill of computer literacy is needed by the undergraduates to able to manipulate the devices, their family background exposes them to computers early in life that will help them accept and build confidence and capacity to use e-resources. However, the finding implies that the regression model does not explain a substantial amount of the variance in the use of e-resources among undergraduates in North-west Nigeria. Therefore, it can be said that there is no strong joint correlation among the variables. The weak correlation and low explanatory power suggest that these variables, either individually or together, do not significantly influence the use of e-resources. This implies that other variables not considered in the model may have influence on the use of e-resources, hence, the need to identify them for a better insight. Hypothetically, there is a statistically significant correlation among undergraduates' computer literacy, parents' education level, and the use of e-resources in university libraries in North-West, Nigeria, however, while it has statistically significant correlation, it is weak, still indicating that there are other variables that may also possibly play significant roles in influencing the use of e-resources. Interestingly, there is no literature to either support or disagree with this finding.

Implications of the findings

The findings of the study regarding computer literacy shows a positive weak relationship between undergraduates' computer literacy skills and their use of e-resources in university libraries in North-West, Nigeria. This raises important considerations for educational institutions. It implies that while improving undergraduates' computer literacy is of immense benefit, it is not the only factor that influences students' use of e-resources. Other elements, such as access to digital technology, awareness, students' motivation,

and familiarity with specific e-resources, may play crucial roles and therefore need to be addressed.

A positive weak relationship exists between undergraduates' parent's education level and their use of e-resources in university libraries in North-West, Nigeria. This relationship implies that as parents' education levels increase, there is a slight increase in the possibility that their children will use e-resources. Efforts should be made to ensure that students make use of the e-resources, irrespective of their parents' background.

The joint correlation results indicate a positive weak significant correlation between computer literacy, parents' education level and undergraduates' use of e-resources in university libraries in North-West, Nigeria. This correlation, though weak, underscores the importance of computer literacy as a critical skill in today's educational landscape, where access to information increasingly relies on technology and socioeconomic status (parents' educational level) which influences access to technology. Today's higher education is increasingly integrating technology into learning environments, this implies that students with strong digital skills are better positioned to use e-resources effectively. By implication, students from higher parents' educational level may have greater access to technology and educational resources, enabling them to develop digital literacy more effectively, while students from lower parents' educational level may face barriers, such as limited access to the internet or computers, which could hinder their ability to engage with e-resources. Therefore, universities need to prioritize computer literacy training, ensuring that all the students irrespective of their parents' educational backgrounds have the skills necessary to access and utilize digital resources optimally. This finding calls for targeted interventions to bridge the digital divide and promote equitable access to educational technologies.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:

1. Universities in North-West, Nigeria should consider implementing comprehensive training programs that will not only focus on improving computer literacy but also educate students on the effective use of e-resources. Additionally, increasing access to technology and providing continuous support can further enhance students' ability to leverage digital resources in their academic work.

2. Universities should establish parental engagement platforms to encourage parental involvement in education, where they would be encouraged to support their children by providing them with affordable digital tools. Libraries, on the other hand, are to implement programmes aimed at increasing awareness about e-resources, by organizing informational sessions and/or workshops to help parents appreciate the importance of e-resources and how to support their children in using them.
3. Universities and libraries should invest in a wide range of e-resources and ensure that they are easily accessible to all students irrespective of their parents' educational background. They also have to consider a more comprehensive approach to enhancing e-resource usage, such as digital literacy and financial aid to take care of students from low socio-economic backgrounds beyond just focusing on computer literacy and parental education levels.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, the study have determined that a positive but weak relationship exists between computer literacy, parents' educational level and undergraduates' use of e-resources in university libraries in North-West, Nigeria. it also shows that there is a significant correlation amongst them. The study provides insights on how computer literacy and parents' educational level correlate with undergraduates' use of e-resources in North-West Nigeria and highlights the importance of addressing computer literacy and parental education in promoting the use of e-resources among undergraduates. The provision of e-resources by the universities and students' possession of computer literacy, their parents' educational level are associated with the undergraduates' weak use of e-resources, indicating roles of other factors. Therefore, the weak positive significant joint correlation emphasises the need for universities and other stakeholders to consider a more comprehensive approach that will enhance e-resources usage, beyond just focusing on computer literacy and parental educational levels.

Declaration Statement

This research is part of the first author's PhD dissertation, titled "Digital Literacy and Socioeconomic Variables as Correlates to Undergraduates Use of Electronic Information Resources in University Libraries in North-West, Nigeria", under the supervision of Prof A. U. Echedom at the Department of Library and Information Science, Faculty of

Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria. Hence, the data used for this study is from the PhD Dissertation dataset.

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